

ORGANIZATION OF SPEECH THERAPY IN ONLINE EDUCATION CONDITIONS

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***Abstract.** The development trends of the modern world lead to the fact that any work can be organized on the online platform, including the educational process. The field of special pedagogy, in particular speech therapy, is no exception. Computer programs, such as Skype or Zoom, help to successfully carry out work aimed at overcoming speech disorders in children, teenagers and adults. Speech therapy online work is a good alternative to organizing speech therapy classes if it is not possible to visit a speech therapist and organize an in the class [1].*

The introduction of computer technology today is a new approach in the educational process. Speech therapists not only did not stand aside, but were also actively involved in the process of widespread use of computer technology. Computer technologies are a powerful and effective tool for corrective work. They are included in the structure of traditional individual speech therapy classes as additional innovative elements, and in distance learning as the main ones. Currently, computer technologies are an important part of the education sector [2].

Keywords and phrases: *online learning, special pedagogy, speech therapy work, computer programs, information technology, speech disorders, cooperation*

INTRODUCTION. The result of the modern development trends of the world is the reality where any activity, including educational process, can be organized on online platform. The sphere of special pedagogy, in particular speech therapy, is no exception. Computer programs such as “Skype” or “Zoom” help to successfully carry out work aimed at overcoming speech disorders in children, adolescents and adults. Online speech therapy option is a good alternative opportunity for organizing speech therapy lessons, when it is not possible to attend a speech therapist and organize the class face-to-face [1] [5].

The introduction of computer technologies is a new approach in the educational process today. The speech therapists were not only not excluded, but also actively involved in the process of wide use of Information and Computer Technologies (ICT). Computer technologies represent a powerful and effective tool in correctional work. They are included in the structure of traditional individual speech therapy lessons as additional innovative elements, and in remote learning conditions as the main ones. Now computer technology is an integral part in educational sphere [2] [4].

FUNDAMENTAL ISSUES: In pandemic situation, almost all types of work: education, consultation, training, including the sphere of special pedagogy, in particular, speech therapy, were carried out online. Speech therapy process could be built based on the use of ICT and the use of Internet resources, which is different from traditional ways of teaching. Although both the specialists and the children were not ready to conduct training in that online format, nevertheless, in this way, the basis for cooperation establishment with the parent was made. Before the pandemic, speech therapy started and ended in the speech therapy room, but now with the online format, the involvement and participation of parents, especially parents of preschool and elementary school children, has increased dramatically.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY: The objective of this study is to identify the readiness level and attitude of parents of speech-impaired children and speech therapists working with these children towards the work carried out in online learning conditions. Importantly, there has been an evolution in parental attitudes toward distance learning from skeptical disregard to inspired team collaboration. With the participation and support of parents with the speech therapist, not only the preparation of the organs of the speech apparatus, but also the correct pronunciation of sounds, reinforcement of sounds, differentiation of sounds and other activities were successfully carried out. The need for closer and more active cooperation with pedagogues, pedagogue-psychologist, social pedagogue and pedagogue allows to implement multidisciplinary complex support for children with developmental disorders, particularly speech disorders [3].

Since the distance education implies individual learning, there is a problem of developing communication skills, desire and opportunities for students with peers. To solve this problem, speech therapists have actively used such a type of distance class as a teleconference. The speech therapist could communicate with two or three students at the same time through the "Skype" program (all video conference participants see each other on the screen). Also, school group events were held, in which the students participated with great interest, they found many new friends and became more friendly with each other [4].

ESSENCE OF STUDY

In general, there are several creative and positive results in distance education situation of speech therapy. Information technologies provide an opportunity to carry out more distinctive creative activities not only for the speech therapist, but also for the students. The speech therapists were able to compile educational materials and organize speech therapy classes using audio and video information, games and playing exercises, including online classes (the speech therapist makes a tab with a game, video or other information and opens it at the necessary moment of the course, showing it on the screen of the "Skype" program in display mode"). Despite the

created pandemic conditions, there has always been constant access to Internet resources, which in turn allowed speech therapists to use information-methodical and educational material, opportunities for students (and their parents), to implement interactive cooperation with the educational environment of the school (e-mail, "Skype" " " program, through the school website) the speech therapist has posted relevant information for parents and students. The speech therapist also promptly modified, supplemented and updated the materials, used the possibilities of creating high-quality didactic materials and games based on Internet resources. For example, various exercises, games, quizzes and tests, various programs, including those in animational format, in the form of video slides or presentations, training manuals, etc. [5].

Conducting distance training is fundamentally a creative process, and each specialist creates his own methodological-didactic and informative-communicational base on the basis of information technologies. The practice of remote work proves that with proper organization of class hours and adaptation of existing programs, this format of conducting classes, taking into account the individual requests and desires of the student, provides tangible positive results in education of schoolchildren with speech problems.

Thus, if desired, the use of existing computer technologies in the course of distance learning becomes effective, interesting, and methodologically complete. We studied and conducted a survey among speech therapists regarding the organization of speech therapy in online learning conditions. The analysis of the results of the survey conducted with 26 speech therapists showed that during the pandemic, 90% of speech therapists also worked remotely in practice. Below is the data from our survey results.

Diagram 1. Implementation of speech therapy in distance according to results of a survey conducted with speech therapists

When asked why children could miss speech therapy lessons, 42% of specialists replied it was due to the children's health condition, 31% due to the lack of necessary tools and Internet failure, 19% due to communication failure and the child's lack of concentration, and 8% answered that it was caused by the child's behavioral problem. Because there were cases when the child refused to approach the screen, and the work was done through the parent, that is, the task was given and explained to the parent, after which the parent did it with the child. And the video representing the entire work process was sent to the specialist.

Diagram 2. Reasons for missing a speech therapy lesson according to results of a survey of speech therapists

We were interested in the question of whether children's motivation was fully satisfied during online lessons. 46% of the speech therapists who participated in the survey stated that the children's motivation was not sufficient at all, 12% mentioned

that it was mostly sufficient, and 42% stated that the lessons became complete only when the speech therapists made the work process even more interesting by using digital technologies, applying the method of encouragement (D3).

Diagram 3. Children's motivation for online lessons according to results of a survey conducted with speech therapists

We also tried to find out what kind of interest the children had in online lessons. 56.6% of the speech therapists stated that the children were interested, and 44.4% stated that they were not always interested (D4).

Diagram 4. Children's interest in speech therapy lessons according to results of a survey conducted with speech therapists

We tried to find out what were the negative aspects of online speech therapy lesson on the point of view of the speech therapists who participated in the survey. 69% of speech therapists mentioned the lack of face-to-face contact as a negative aspect of the options we proposed, and 31% mentioned the deterioration of communication and the child's lack of concentration during the lesson. (D5)

Diagram 5. Disadvantages of remote lessons according to results of a survey conducted with speech therapists

And when asked about the positive aspects of online speech therapy lessons for children, 31% of speech therapists mentioned the saving of resources (travel expenses, time), 8% stated that online lessons make it possible to use modern technologies even more at work during the lesson, 19% mentioned the high involvement of parents, and 42% found it difficult to answer the question (D6).

Diagram 6. Positive aspects of in distance speech therapy according to survey results

When asked what methods speech therapists have used during the distance speech therapy, they mostly indicated the ways of relying on encouragement, making some videos and presenting the material through them. The experts mentioned the following options: application of didactic games, familiarization and application of appropriate intervention techniques to parents. The specialists also noted that in order to overcome fatigue, the program was often modified so that the child could participate and be involved in the entire work process. However, there were

specialists who did not use any particular method. We also wanted to find out whether the duration of speech therapy was preserved, that is, 20-40 minutes, or whether there were some changes. 35% of specialists stated that the period was maintained, and 65% stated that there were some changes in the duration of work. In the online format, specialists worked for a shorter period of time (D7).

Diagram 7. Changes in the duration of in distance speech therapy

Diagram 8. Effectiveness of remote speech therapy evaluated by 1-10-point system, according to a survey conducted with speech therapists

Specialists tried to evaluate the effectiveness of online speech therapy evaluating it by 1-10 point grading system. 2.5% of them rated 2 points, 2.5% - 3 points, .5% - 8 points, 15% - 4 points, 20% - 5 points, 25% - 6 points, and 30% is 7 points (D8).

CONCLUSION: Summarizing the data obtained during the survey, it can be stated that according to specialists, children missed online speech therapy lessons due to their health condition, lack of necessary tools, communication failure, as well as

because of the child's lack of concentration. The specialists also mentioned that during online speech therapy lessons, children's motivation was generally not enough to complete a full session, although there were specialists who mentioned that it was full especially when the speech therapists have made the learning process even more interesting by using digital technologies, also they have always applied the method of encouragement, and also emphasized the involvement of parents in the activities being carried out.

The majority of specialists stated that children were nevertheless interested in online speech therapy lessons. The negative aspects of online speech therapy lessons are the lack of contact, the deterioration of communication and the child's lack of concentration during the lesson.

References:

1. <https://www.who.int/dg/speeches/detail/who>
2. <https://en.unesco.org/>
3. <https://shamardina.ru/articles/kak-logopedu-rabotat-onlayn?fbclid=IwAR3nvgbUU-QbEdJ1n8T0ihOhmgxLzlclzvK1JE2lx7NdR0b25TCfMnDYqdM>
4. <https://infourok.ru/statya-na-temu-luchshie-praktiki-distancionnogo-obucheniya-v-rabote-uchitelya-logopeda-4253831.html?fbclid=IwAR3nvgbUU-QbEdJ1n8T0ihOhmgxLzlclzvK1JE2lx7NdR0b25TCfMnDYqdM>
5. http://library.isu.ru/ru/resources/e-library/conf_works_ISU/Prof_Soderzhanie/Prof-98.pdf?fbclid=IwAR05wDqrvXpDfiSCCAcKjqEG66CIItGsiJ62PXnF_uoYscene4K6oHxhYi-9w